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Research Article

**OBSERVATORY STUDY ON THE BRDU ANALOG: IT IS
RESPONSIBLE FOR THE DNA AND ASSOCIATED WITH THE
DNA**¹Syeda Sabah Zahra, ²Uroosa Zahara, ³Sadaf Zahra
¹Jinnah Hospital Lahore.**Article Received:** August 2020**Accepted:** September 2020**Published:** October 2020**Abstract:**

The destruction of the beta cells is the major part of form 1 diabetes. It is observed that according to the anti-gad and anti ia2 these two anti-bodies effect the destruction of beta cells. It is observed that these two auto antibodies effects on the destruction of the beta cells. It is observed that the according to these two anti-bodies the destruction of beta cells increases it is also observed that the role of beta cells the role of beta cells it is responsible for the proper observance of the insulin. If the insulin cell not proper observes in the beta cells it causes the form 1 diabetes so for this theory you observe the role of insulin. So for the avoidance of these strategies it is observed that the beta cells and insulin what they play role in our body. So for the treatment of the form 1 diabetes we uses the method of the insulin therapy it is observed that the we trying to the multiples the beta cells so that the proper insulin is starting production and patients start healing. In the easy way it says that he we reverse the form 1 diabetes by using the multiplying the beta cells. In this study the mice must be included it is observed that the human has the type 1 diabetes we apply a multiplying method on it. We use the another analog in this study these analogs are called the brdu analog. It is observed that the brdu analog is responsible for the dna and it is generally associated with the dna. It is observed that the brdu plays a same role in the human like a beta cells plays a role in the human body. So we study the brdu and beta cells both to clarify that what is actually happened.

Keywords: Brdu, beta cell multiplication, human, DNA, role, mayo hospital Lahore auto antibodies, proper observance of glucose.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Syeda Sabah Zahra,**
Jinnah Hospital Lahore.

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INTRODUCTION:

By the prevention and cure of a diabetes 1 patient we use the method of the multiplication in this method we multiply the beta cells which is responsible for the proper observance of insulin in the blood it is talk earlier in previous studied that the destruction of beta cells causes the form 1 diabetes [1]. So it is clear that insulin what plays in proper observance of glucose [2]. It is also observed in this study that this brdu plays an important role in the human [3]. It is observed that the brdu plays a same role in the human as the beta cells plays a role in the human body [4]. It is also observed that the brdu is not having one use it has a main role in the overall biology [5]. By using the different condition by using the different condition it is observed that the role of brdu in the beta cells had been observed we observes it by using the monitoring of the destruction of DNA [6]. Now from this you observe that the brdu and DNA and how it's associated with the each other [7]. It is observed that the multiplication of the beta cells we have to studied the role of the brdu it is observed that the brdu resists the from the successfully mitosis [8]. The question is that the is the brdu is associated with the s phase entry it plays what role in the s phase entry it is observe that the it is a very un relevant process during the dna destruction [9]. It is important to clear the role of brdu in the destruction of beta cells during the destruction of the it is very important to reveal this study [10]. The major goals of this study is to find the all the possibilities activities of brdu and the histone family member and any other causes [11]. The mayo hospital Lahore takes this clear and a danger so that its takes it's very important so that this role of brdu and what it have to do [12].

METHODOLOGY:

In this study the human including in this study are must from the age of 11 to 13 week. It is also kept in eye from the age of the 60 to 70 week old. The sex include in this study are both male and the female. We leave them in the breeding balcony. It is observed that the human has access to another human. It is observed that the islet injection must be inoculated in the all the human. We performed a different types of the test and study on it is observed that the for dispersed study islets were have the digested with some other chemicals. We gave them a 24 hour treatment.

RESULT:

It is observed that the human beta cells in these cells we find the brdu cells in the humans of the form the islets treatment following figure shows that the how brdu and other chemical test had been conducted and then what role of a brdu in this. It is observed that the

in the beta cells that some beta cells have the human islet culture. It is observed that the it is observed that the human that are removed from this study how their blood cells effects with in the 72 hours. It is observed that the almost the 6 percent glucose given to all the cases it is observed that these human AN A' B C D D' it is observed that the after from some incultion of the glucose how the body changes and blood cells changes it selves as shown in the following figure. It is also observed that the two proliferative stimull how the it increases in the brdu and the frequency of these twos. As shown in the following figure.

In this studied we performed a test in which most of the data over laping and effect the whole result as shown in the following figure we show it by using the venn diagram it is mathematically term which is used to find the over laping result or the visual result as shown in the following figure. In the following figure different shows that the data in the form of table by using the young old category and the brdu and other category we take the young old category on the horizontal line and brdu category on the other vertical line as shown in figure. All data shows according to the obtained result. This result shows according to the movements of the cells after inculting the insulin.

DISCUSSION:

In this study we have to find the brdu [14]. It is observed that the we uses the human it is observed that the young human is not more old then the 11 months and it is also observed that the young human is not more than the 61 it is observed in this study that the after inculcating the insulin it how effects the whole study it is also observed that the how the rates kept on easy body temperature and have the allowance in the breeding all. Our studied performed in the mayo hospital Lahore clearly shows the all matters and all studied by using different diagrams by using Venn diagram and by graph of the different type.

CONCLUSION:

By using the different condition, the role of brdu in the beta cells had been observed. We observed it by using the monitoring of the destruction of dna. It is observed that the brdu plays a same role in the human as the beta cells plays a role in the human body. It is also observed that the brdu is not having one use it has a main role in the overall biology [15]. It is observed that the it is observed that the human that are removed from this study how their blood cells effects with in the 72 hours [16]. It is observed that the almost the 6 percent glucose given to all the cases it is observed that these human A' B C D' it is

observed that the after from some incultion of the glucose how the body changes and blood cells changes [17].

REFERENCES:

- Sharma, R. B., Darko, C., Zheng, X., Gablaski, B., & Alonso, L. C. (2019). DNA damage does not cause BrdU labeling of human or human β -cells. *Diabetes*, 68(5), 975-987.
- Lixia, S., Yao, K., Kaijun, W., Deqiang, L., Huajun, H., Xiangwei, G., ... & Wei, W. (2006). Effects of 1.8 GHz radiofrequency field on DNA damage and expression of heat shock protein 70 in human lens epithelial cells. *Mutation Research/Fundamental and Molecular Mechanisms of Mutagenesis*, 602(1-2), 135-142.
- Di Leonardo, A., Linke, S. P., Clarkin, K., & Wahl, G. M. (1994). DNA damage triggers a prolonged p53-dependent G1 arrest and long-term induction of Cip1 in normal human fibroblasts. *Genes & development*, 8(21), 2540-2551.
- Cardus, A., Uryga, A. K., Walters, G., & Erusalimsky, J. D. (2013). SIRT6 protects human endothelial cells from DNA damage, telomere dysfunction, and senescence. *Cardiovascular research*, 97(3), 571-579.
- Herbig, U., Jobling, W. A., Chen, B. P., Chen, D. J., & Sedivy, J. M. (2004). Telomere shortening triggers senescence of human cells through a pathway involving ATM, p53, and p21CIP1, but not p16INK4a. *Molecular cell*, 14(4), 501-513.
- Wang, P., Alvarez-Perez, J. C., Felsenfeld, D. P., Liu, H., Sivendran, S., Bender, A., ... & Stewart, A. F. (2015). A high-throughput chemical screen reveals that harmine-mediated inhibition of DYRK1A increases human pancreatic beta cell replication. *Nature medicine*, 21(4), 383-388.
- Bartkova, J., Rezaei, N., Liontos, M., Karakaidos, P., Kletsas, D., Issaeva, N., ... & Takaoka, M. (2006). Oncogene-induced senescence is part of the tumorigenesis barrier imposed by DNA damage checkpoints. *Nature*, 444(7119), 633-637.
- Hopkins, K. M., Auerbach, W., Wang, X. Y., Hande, M. P., Hang, H., Wolgemuth, D. J., ... & Lieberman, H. B. (2004). Deletion of human rad9 causes abnormal cellular responses to DNA damage, genomic instability, and embryonic lethality. *Molecular and cellular biology*, 24(16), 7235-7248.
- Verdun, R. E., & Karlseder, J. (2006). The DNA damage machinery and homologous recombination pathway act consecutively to protect human telomeres. *Cell*, 127(4), 709-720.
- Hyka-Nouspikel, N., Desmarais, J., Gokhale, P. J., Jones, M., Meuth, M., Andrews, P. W., & Nouspikel, T. (2012). Deficient DNA damage response and cell cycle checkpoints lead to accumulation of point mutations in human embryonic stem cells. *Stem Cells*, 30(9), 1901-1910.
- Yang, Q., Hergenahn, M., Weninger, A., & Bartsch, H. (1999). Cigarette smoke induces direct DNA damage in the human B-lymphoid cell line Raji. *Carcinogenesis*, 20(9), 1769-1775.
- Ruiz-Ramos, R., Lopez-Carrillo, L., Rios-Perez, A. D., De Vizcaya-Ruiz, A., & Cebrian, M. E. (2009). Sodium arsenite induces ROS generation, DNA oxidative damage, HO-1 and c-Myc proteins, NF- κ B activation and cell proliferation in human breast cancer MCF-7 cells. *Mutation Research/Genetic Toxicology and Environmental Mutagenesis*, 674(1-2), 109-115.
- Linke, S. P., Clarkin, K. C., Di Leonardo, A., Tsou, A., & Wahl, G. M. (1996). A reversible, p53-dependent G0/G1 cell cycle arrest induced by ribonucleotide depletion in the absence of detectable DNA damage. *Genes & development*, 10(8), 934-947.
- Ruiz-Ramos, R., Lopez-Carrillo, L., Rios-Perez, A. D., De Vizcaya-Ruiz, A., & Cebrian, M. E. (2009). Sodium arsenite induces ROS generation, DNA oxidative damage, HO-1 and c-Myc proteins, NF- κ B activation and cell proliferation in human breast cancer MCF-7 cells. *Mutation Research/Genetic Toxicology and Environmental Mutagenesis*, 674(1-2), 109-115.
- Linke, S. P., Clarkin, K. C., Di Leonardo, A., Tsou, A., & Wahl, G. M. (1996). A reversible, p53-dependent G0/G1 cell cycle arrest induced by ribonucleotide depletion in the absence of detectable DNA damage. *Genes & development*, 10(8), 934-947.
- Rieck, S., Zhang, J., Li, Z., Liu, C., Naji, A., Takane, K. K., ... & Kaestner, K. H. (2012). Overexpression of hepatocyte nuclear factor-4 α initiates cell cycle entry, but is not sufficient to promote β -cell expansion in human islets. *Molecular endocrinology*, 26(9), 1590-1602.
- Petersen, A. B., Wulf, H. C., Gniadecki, R., & Gajkowska, B. (2004). Dihydroxyacetone, the active tanning ingredient in sunless tanning lotions, induces DNA damage, cell-cycle block and apoptosis in cultured HaCaT keratinocytes. *Mutation Research/Genetic Toxicology and Environmental Mutagenesis*, 560(2), 173-186.